

Modular and User-Space Prototyping of a PCI-Based Cryptographic Accelerator in QEMU

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Abstract—This work presents a prototyping approach for a PCI-based cryptographic accelerator in QEMU. The design avoids frequent QEMU rebuilds and leverages the UIO framework to bypass kernel driver development. The prototype demonstrates the feasibility of rapid hardware/software co-design for RISC-V environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptographic accelerators play a crucial role in modern computing systems by offloading computationally intensive operations such as encryption, decryption, and hashing. Their use is essential in secure communication, data protection, and performance-sensitive applications. At the same time, hardware/software co-design has become increasingly important, where researchers and developers need to prototype new accelerator designs quickly and evaluate them in realistic environments. QEMU, as a widely used open-source emulator, has emerged as a popular platform for this purpose because it enables system-level testing without requiring immediate access to physical hardware. However, conventional approaches to extending QEMU with new accelerators face significant challenges. Each modification to accelerator logic typically requires a full QEMU rebuild, slowing down experimentation. Furthermore, integrating a custom device often necessitates writing and maintaining kernel drivers, which is both time-consuming and complex for early-stage prototyping. These limitations motivate the need for a more modular, flexible approach that enables rapid testing of accelerator designs while minimizing development overhead [1].

Current accelerator prototyping in QEMU is often slow and rigid, as each modification to the accelerator logic typically requires rebuilding the emulator. This lack of flexibility makes it difficult to experiment with new functionality or rapidly iterate on design changes. In addition, prototyping usually involves developing kernel drivers, which adds significant complexity and overhead, especially in early stages of research. To address these challenges, this work introduces a PCI-based cryptographic accelerator in QEMU that leverages shared libraries (.so files) to modularize accelerator logic. By separating the accelerator functions into dynamically linked libraries, changes can be applied without recompiling QEMU, thereby streamlining experimentation. On the software side, the Userspace I/O (UIO) framework is employed to bypass kernel driver development, enabling direct interaction with the emulated accelerator from user space. The approach is demonstrated in a RISC-V Linux environment, showcasing

a more efficient workflow for rapid hardware/software co-design. This work introduces a flexible prototyping methodology that reduces development overhead while enabling rapid experimentation.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Integration with QEMU

The prototype began with modifications to the QEMU source tree in order to introduce a custom PCI device. The process can be summarized in the following steps:

- 1) **Setup of QEMU environment** – The QEMU source code and its dependencies were installed to provide a base for modification.
- 2) **Addition of a new source file** – A file named `crypto_accel.c` was created under the `hw/pci/` directory. This file defines the custom cryptographic accelerator, including register mappings, initialization routines, and the interface to the guest system.
- 3) **Build system integration** – The `meson.build` configuration was updated to include `crypto_accel.c` in the compilation process. This ensured that the new source file was recognized and compiled as part of the PCI subsystem.
- 4) **Device registration** – With the file compiled into QEMU, the emulator was extended to support the new accelerator as a virtual PCI device, laying the groundwork for integration with shared libraries and user-space access mechanisms.

The prototype began with modifications to the QEMU source tree in order to introduce a custom PCI device. This integration was carried out in several stages. First, the QEMU environment was prepared by obtaining and configuring the source code together with its dependencies. A new source file, `crypto_accel.c`, was then created inside the `hw/pci/` directory. This file defines the cryptographic accelerator, including the register interface, memory-mapped I/O (MMIO) handlers, and initialization routines. To ensure that the new device was compiled, the build system was extended by adding the line `pci_ss.add(files('crypto_accel.c'))` in the `meson.build` configuration file. With this in place, QEMU recognized the file as part of the PCI subsystem.

The core functionality of the device is connected dynamically through a shared object (.so) library. The `load_crypto_core()` routine in `crypto_accel.c` invokes `dlopen` and `dlsym` to fetch function pointers

from `libcrypto_core.so`. These pointers provide cryptographic operations that can be executed when MMIO writes occur from the guest system. This modular design avoids embedding fixed algorithms in QEMU itself, instead enabling flexibility by swapping or extending accelerator logic through user-space libraries. Finally, the device is registered as a PCI component with vendor and device IDs, and the UIO mechanism (`uio_pci_generic`) is used in the Linux guest to access the accelerator without requiring kernel driver development.

B. Dynamic Linking to Shared Library

The accelerator implementation was separated into a shared object (`.so`) file [2]. Two functions were exported:

- `crypto_core_init()`
- `crypto_core_run()`

These functions take input values and return encrypted results. The QEMU device model dynamically loads and calls these functions, allowing modifications without recompiling the entire QEMU binary. To increase flexibility and avoid frequent rebuilds, the device model links the shared library at runtime using `dlopen()` and `dlsym()`. This allows the accelerator logic to be modified independently, making it possible to experiment with different cryptographic implementations by simply replacing the `.so` file. For demonstration purposes, a simple implementation was provided where the initialization function prints a message, and the execution function performs a lightweight transformation (`input ^ 0xdeadbeef`). This approach illustrates the ease of rapid prototyping and iteration in hardware/software co-design environments.

C. Creating VM based on RISC-V in QEMU

To evaluate the proposed cryptographic accelerator, a virtual machine (VM) was set up using the RISC-V architecture in QEMU. Two approaches were considered. The first involved building a minimal Linux image with BusyBox, which provides a lightweight user-space environment suitable for testing. This was achieved by cross-compiling the Linux kernel and root filesystem for RISC-V, packaging them into a disk image, and launching them under QEMU. The second approach relied on readily available open-source RISC-V images in `.qcow2` format, which simplified the setup process and avoided manual compilation. Once a working image was obtained, the VM was started with the custom cryptographic accelerator enabled using the following command:

Listing 1: Launching RISC-V VM with custom PCI accelerator

```
qemu-system-riscv64 \
  -machine virt \
  -cpu rv64 \
  -m 1G \
  -device virtio-blk-device,drive=hd \
  -drive file=image.qcow2,if=none,id=hd \
  -device virtio-net-device,netdev=net \
  -netdev user,id=net,hostfwd=tcp::2222-:22 \
```

```
-bios /usr/lib/riscv64-linux-gnu/opensbi
  /generic/fw_jump.elf \
-kernel /usr/lib/u-boot/qemu-riscv64_s
  mode/uboot.elf \
-object rng-random,filename=/dev/
  urandom,id=rng \
-device virtio-rng-device,rng=rng \
-device crypto-accel \
-nographic \
-append "root=LABEL=rootfs_console=ttyS0"
```

D. Guest Environment Setup

Within the guest virtual machine, the required kernel modules `uio` and `uio_pci_generic` were loaded [3]. The virtual accelerator device was then bound to the UIO framework, allowing user-space applications to directly interact with the hardware registers.

A user-space C program was developed to facilitate this interaction. First, the program opens a `sysfs` file using `fopen()` and reads the memory mapping size with `fscanf()`. This size determines the extent of the memory region that must be mapped for user-space access. The UIO device is then opened with `open()`, establishing a file descriptor through which the accelerator can be accessed.

The memory region corresponding to the device's registers is mapped into the process address space using `mmap()`, allowing the program to directly read from and write to hardware registers. Values are written to specific offsets to trigger the accelerator's computation, and the resulting output is read back from designated result registers. After the transaction, the mapped memory is released using `munmap()`, and the UIO device is closed with `close()`.

This approach ensures that the guest system can interact with the virtual accelerator entirely from user space, bypassing the need for a kernel driver while maintaining safe and controlled access. The code effectively demonstrates the read/write workflow for PCI register interaction and serves as a template for rapid prototyping of new accelerator functionality.

E. User-Space Interaction

To facilitate testing and interaction with the virtual accelerator, custom user-space scripts were developed. These scripts directly access the PCI Base Address Register (BAR) regions of the emulated device, allowing values to be written to specific registers and results to be read back. For example, a test value such as `0x12345678` can be written to the input register of the accelerator. The accelerator processes this input using the dynamically linked shared library functions (`crypto_core_run()`), and the resulting encrypted value is subsequently read from the result register. This approach enables rapid verification of the accelerator's functionality entirely from user space, without requiring kernel driver development, and demonstrates the practical workflow for sending data to and retrieving results from the emulated PCI device.

The complete source code for the PCI-based accelerator and user-space scripts is available at: https://github.com/Ahad-Dar1/crypto_prototyping.

III. RESULTS

The prototype demonstrates successful end-to-end communication between the guest virtual machine and the PCI-based cryptographic accelerator. Guest applications interact with the accelerator through the UIO framework, sending input data from a user-space program to be processed by the shared library (.so). The encrypted outputs are then returned to the application, validating the correct operation of the accelerator and the dynamic linking mechanism.

This approach proves flexible, allowing experimentation with different cryptographic algorithms without the need for extensive development or repeated QEMU recompilation. Development iterations are therefore significantly accelerated, as only the shared library needs to be updated to test new functionality.

Figure 1 illustrates an example workflow, showing the value sent from the guest application and the corresponding encrypted result received from the accelerator.

```
root@debian:~# modprobe uio
root@debian:~# modprobe uio_pci_generic
root@debian:~# echo "1234 5678" | tee /sys/
d
1234 5678
[ 156.473621] uio_pci_generic 0000:00:0
rt for interrupts?
root@debian:~# ./newgen
Wrote 0x12345678, result = 0xcc99e897
root@debian:~#
```

Fig. 1: sending data via userspace app to be encrypted

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The proposed approach successfully demonstrates a flexible and efficient method for prototyping PCI-based accelerators within QEMU. By combining UIO with dynamic linking to shared libraries, developers can iterate on accelerator logic quickly without modifying the kernel or recompiling the simulator. This significantly reduces development time and simplifies testing of new cryptographic algorithms or hardware functions.

For future work, several directions are envisioned. First, the framework can be extended to receive input directly from RTL implementations through a wrapper in the shared library (.so) file, allowing hardware designs simulated via Verilator or other tools to be seamlessly integrated. Second, the methodology can be expanded to support multiple accelerators running concurrently in the virtual environment, enabling more complex co-design scenarios. Finally, benchmarking and performance evaluation of cryptographic operations on the virtual accelerators can be performed, providing insights into efficiency and potential bottlenecks compared to software-only implementations.

Overall, this work lays the foundation for rapid hardware/software co-design and provides a practical environment for experimentation and validation of custom accelerator designs in RISC-V systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents a practical and efficient approach for prototyping PCI-based cryptographic accelerators within a QEMU virtual environment. By leveraging the Userspace I/O (UIO) framework and dynamic linking to shared libraries, the proposed method eliminates the need for kernel driver development and avoids repeated recompilation of the simulator. The prototype demonstrates that developers can rapidly iterate on accelerator logic by modifying only the shared object (.so) file, while the QEMU device model and guest environment remain unchanged.

The approach enables direct user-space interaction with the emulated hardware through memory-mapped I/O, simplifying testing and verification workflows. Using this framework, hardware/software co-design for RISC-V systems becomes more flexible, allowing experimentation with different cryptographic algorithms without extensive development overhead.

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